

EOSC - Who needs to do what?

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with contributions from Andrea Herdegen, Ignacio Blanquer Espert, Marialuisa Lavitrano, Robert Jones, Sara Garavelli, Sarah Jones, Stefan Hanslik, Suzanne Dumouchel, Volker Beckmann, Wilhelm Widmark (EOSC Board of Directors and EOSC-Pillar Steering Board Representatives)

Marie

EOSC – Who needs to do what?

Andreas

Hello and welcome to today's episode of Stories of Data - the Open.Science.Talk.

Marie

Join us and take the dive to get deeper insights into the magical and mystical world of the European Open Science Cloud (in short: EOSC).

Andreas

More precisely: In order to support researchers to implement Open Science, our topic is: Who needs to do what? Like our last episode, this one is based on contributions of the EOSC Association Board of Directors and the Steering Board Representatives.

Marie

So, once more we give the floor to our EOSC-VIPs! And thanks to them we have again a huge pile of very interesting answers. I have them here.

Andreas

I'm already curious about them! Take a look at this one: "In order to support researchers to implement Open Science: Who needs to do what?"

Marie

Sorry, wait a second. So this time we do not talk about the European Open Science Cloud, but about Open Science in general, yes?

Andreas

Yes - well, open science is more than EOSC, but EOSC is a very important building block to make the exchange and re-use of research data possible. To make it happen, researchers, politics at the EU-level and also on the national level have to cooperate. Favourable regulatory surroundings, ideas and active involvement from research and financial support from national governments and the EU - all these contribute to a successful implementation.

Marie

I see. Thanks. So all those are the stakeholders of EOSC and also of Open Science, right? And we want to know, who needs to take what kind of action in order to push things forward regarding Open Science?

Andreas

Yes, how these actors can support researchers so they are implementing Open Science. What is needed? That was the question and here is one of the answers: “There are many dimensions that need to be explored. Open Science requires effort and skills to annotate data, homogenise metadata, register them, provide reproducible environments and release all the assets (data, software, processing environments, publications, etc.) in a consistent and coherent environment. We need to lower the barrier, reducing the effort, standardise protocols, setup services, provide resources, and improve the recognition of contributors. Therefore, we need effort at all the levels.”

Marie

Wow, quite a long list of open tasks but also straight to the point what is needed: Effort at all levels will lower the barriers for researchers - by reducing their effort.

Andreas

Indeed. But there is more action required. Also from researchers.

Marie

Sure. Researchers need to ensure an Open Science approach in their work. This includes to have data management plans for projects and to make their research FAIR by design from the very beginning. And FAIR means what, Andreas?

Andreas

Are you testing me?

Marie

Well...please repeat it for all our new listeners.

Andreas

Sure. So the European Open Science Cloud, EOSC, is an initiative that aims to push European academia towards a culture of open research data that is FAIR. It's the acronym for findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR).

Marie

Thank you very much.

So to continue how researchers can support the implementation of Open Science: This is mainly a reflection step in the creation of projects. Researchers need to answer questions like “What do I have to do, so that my work can be re-used by others?”

Andreas

Yes and this question refers to all kinds of data, services, software and also publications of their work.

Marie

This applies to large studies, but also to PhD and master projects.

Andreas

Correct. This approach does not only benefit the research community, but also the individual researcher and for example the hosting lab, as it increases the visibility of the performed studies and last but not least it allows for quality assurance.

Marie

Now we come to the next stakeholders: research performing organisations, like universities. They need to adopt Open Science policies and ensure that Open Science becomes the new normal at the institutional level.

Andreas

This includes to provide the necessary human resources in order to support the provision of FAIR data, the training of the staff on relevant aspects (such as data management plans, how to make data FAIR, where to find supporting services, etc.), and the provision of the required infrastructure.

Marie

The main focus should be here on the human resources, not only providing work power, but also training the next generation in Open Science practices. So to conclude, it is also important that these aspects become part of the curricula at universities.

Andreas

So one important aspect in order to support researchers to implement Open Science is education. We need shared European curricula and a transformation of the system on how we evaluate them in Academia. Should Open Science become the new normal of doing science, then changes at the level of training, careers, and societal engagement are needed.

Marie

We need to build those kind of infrastructures that researchers need to implement Open Science in their work flows easily. The research performing organisations need to have professional staff, like data stewards, to support their researchers.

Andreas

Indeed. Let's have a closer look at the careers in academia: In order to support their researchers, the research performing organisations need to establish new career paths for research infrastructure managers and operators as well as for data managers and data stewards.

Marie

A wide range of roles and skills are needed to support researchers to implement Open Science. Naturally, the services are key in this – it must be easy to create data in a reusable way, adopting common formats and standards for data documentation.

Andreas

So, in concrete terms that means researchers need guidance and support on how to manage and share their data. Many institutions have data stewards or software engineers, who work alongside research teams to facilitate Open Science. Support to openly license data and make it accessible to the broader community is also critical. And repositories play an important role here.

Marie

I agree. Researchers need to be aware of Open Science principles but the universities, disciplinary data repositories and other services play the most important role in enabling the practices by providing the relevant tools and procedures to follow.

Andreas

For sure! Funding organisations need to contribute to this evolution via project calls. All stakeholders in the system need to work for a change in the reward and merit system.

Marie

Yes, and most funding programmes to support EOSC and Open Science progress are financed by the EU member states. So these EU member states need to create the necessary framework to enable EOSC.

Andreas

One aspect here are policies to advance Open Science on the national level, and to align funding with Open Science practices. Where necessary, ministries in charge of research need to coordinate the national effort to mutualise data, services and e-infrastructures and to ensure their connection and federation by the EOSC.

Marie

So to sum it up: The EU has to work on a European legal framework to enable the EOSC and Open Science in general.

Andreas

And the European Commission needs to identify missing links in the EOSC ecosystem and to provide funding in collaboration with the member states to fill in the gaps.

Marie

Well, that is for sure necessary if one of the main objectives of EOSC is to make Open Science the new normal, the new paradigm of science. In this matter, we should continue speaking about research, ideas, knowledge... and a bit less about technology, like tools, services, etc., which is actually not the main concerns of the researchers.

Andreas

Sometimes I feel that we forget why we are all working in this direction. The risk is to be attracted to technology like butterflies to light and to burn one's wings by forgetting the principal: improving the quality of European science.

Marie

Watch out your wings, our dear butterflies out there! Andreas, do we have another answer to the question: “In order to support researchers to implement Open Science: Who needs to do what?”

Andreas

Sure. This one points out that: “Supporting researchers in implementing Open Science is a collective multi-stakeholder effort. The EU and the members have to put in place the right policies and regulations while research performing organisations should educate researchers on the Open Science benefits and reward them in an appropriate manner. The EOSC Partnership has a pivotal role in driving this effort.”

Marie

Sounds good! Especially that politics have to make sure that researchers are able to conduct research in a more efficient and rewarding manner. A single access point is for sure speeding up the research process. And it makes you aware of content you may not have thought relevant for your work. The increased reuse of data also leads to higher citation rates and more credit for your work.

Andreas

We also need to increase the spread of data science competences and culture among researchers as well as to other layers of society, from policy making, to teaching to citizenship at large, to create a truly participative science supported by the whole society.

Marie

Support by the whole society is a huge proposition...not only because it is complicated to understand what is behind "Open Science". Especially because several practices are part of it.

Andreas

I agree. Actually we are all responsible of a part of the implementation of Open Science at different levels and in different purposes. I would say that we are facing a strong difficulty: We want to quickly build the development of Open Science and EOSC but changing habits is a very long process and needs time to avoid frustration and misunderstanding.

Marie

In my opinion the topic Open Science similar to the big buzz word sustainability: It reminds me of this famous song by Elvis Presely „A little less conversation, a little bit more action please“?

Andreas

sings part of the song

Marie

Oh, see, another talent of you.

Andreas

Thanks. I agree. All the stakeholders of Open Science and EOSC, like researchers, funding agencies, services providers, member states etc. They have all expressed their support for Open Science and now EOSC provides a vehicle by which they can follow-up on these good intentions by turning their words into actions.

Marie

Yes. It's all about implementation! And people tend to demand active individual contribution. It is a different discussion how reasonable that is... Anyway, currently Open Science seems to be a lot about "preaching to the converted".

Andreas

You mean, like this podcast?

Marie

Like this podcast. I agree. But we do our best in trying to reach new listeners!

Andreas

By the way, people out there, you can support us in this by promoting this podcast.

Marie

Talking about the demand of active individual contribution.

Andreas

Well, of course we try to attract the attention of those who are already interested in Open Science. They are important multipliers.

Marie

Of course, of course! We need each other! But I think there are two more essential tracks to follow: First, a new generation of researchers. Everyone who starts a degree should know EOSC and understand its principles. As Open Science must be as inclusive as possible, we should put more efforts on the students. If we miss this new generation, it will take years of delay in the adoption of Open Science!

Second, the strongest lever is always money (remember the analogy to sustainability): funding agencies are also multipliers! Already now, data management plans are part of every funding application.

Andreas

Hm...interesting point. I wonder what the people out there think about it.

Marie

We can ask them. I mean, we can try.

Andreas

True. Let's give it a try: Hi, listeners of this podcast! We want to know your answers to the question of today's episode: In order to support researchers to implement Open Science: Who needs to do what? Maybe there are aspects we have not covered today? Maybe you disagree with what we said? Maybe you have a story on this topic? What do you need to implement Open Science? Please drop us a line! The email address is: eosc-pillar.ub@univie.ac.at. Maybe we can make a sequel episode on this topic.

Marie

It would be great to get from the Open Science crowd some more input for the next episodes!

Andreas

Also this episode today was a much bigger collaboration than one might think. It was based on contributions of the EOSC Association Board of Directors and the Steering Board Representatives. Whom we want to thank at this point for their time and interest to take part in this podcast.

Marie

And thanks also to all our listeners for their time and interest! I'm really looking forward to our next podcast episode, and I hope you listeners will join us for that!

Andreas

Until then, take care, stay safe, and stay curious!

Marie

Bye!